

STRAIN RATE DEPENDENT TENSILE PROPERTIES OF INJECTION MOLDED LONG GLASS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Long Fiber reinforced Thermoplastics (LFT) have been used in a lot of industrial fields such as automotive industries because of their excellent moldabilities, productivities, and high mechanical properties compared with injection molded Short Fiber reinforced Thermoplastics (SFT). On the other hand, mechanical properties of LFT are significantly low compared with continuous fiber reinforced plastics. So, improvements of them are still important study subjects. In past studies, there were some reports about the absorbed impact energy of LFT, and LFT showed higher energy absorption property than SFT. However, there have been few studies focused on strength, stiffness and their strain rate dependencies of LFT in impact loading condition. These quantitative evaluations are essential to material design for developments of impact-resistant LFT.

In this study, mechanical properties and strain rate dependency of injection molded long glass fiber reinforced thermoplastics under impact loading were investigated. The effectiveness of longer residual fibers to improvement of impact properties of injection molded composites was indicated. LFT showed higher mechanical properties compared with SFT at any strain rate in this study. Increasing rate of tensile strength in LFT was also much higher than that in SFT, and significant improvement of impact properties of injection molded composites were achieved by longer residual fibers. As a result of observation of micro structures and fracture surfaces after impact tensile test, it was confirmed that the fracture occurred mainly in matrix and fiber/matrix interface in the case of SFT. On the other hand, in LFT specimens, impact tensile loading was effectively transferred to reinforcement glass fibers, and they were broken after impact tensile test. Consequently, it was revealed that strain rate dependency of glass fiber strength resulting from the slow crack growth development led to high impact tensile properties of LFT.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the vehicle weight tends to increase for the purpose of improving the safety and convenience, and applications of fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) have been increasingly promoted. Among them, injection moulded composite is suitable for automotive applications because of high productivity. However, fiber breakage occurs in the moulding process in injection moulded composite, and its mechanical properties are remarkably low compared with continuous fiber composite. Mechanical properties of materials are directly connected to the characteristics of the member and the overall safety of the car. In particular, improvement of impact properties is important in order to apply injection moulded composite to the outer plate and the inner module.

Glass fiber, which is one of the common reinforcement fiber in FRP, is low in cost and its tensile strength is surprisingly increased in impact loading condition.^[1] Therefore, how to reflect the impact strength of the glass fiber is the key in order to improve impact properties of injection moulded

composite while maintaining the productivity and low cost. Long Fiber reinforced Thermoplastics (LFT) is cited as one of the solutions. LFT can keep residual fiber length long after injection moulding compared with normal short fiber pellet^[2]. So, it is expected that high impact strength of glass fiber is utilized and impact properties of injection moulded composite are improved. Although, the effectiveness of LFT in impact loading condition and the influence of residual fiber length on impact properties and impact fracture mechanism are not completely revealed. In this study, impact tensile test was conducted about injection moulded long and short glass fiber reinforced composite. The influence of residual fiber length on impact properties was investigated. We also examined strength development mechanism of LFT in impact loading condition.

2 MATERIALS

In this study, Long Fiber reinforced Thermoplastics (LFT) pellet and Short Fiber reinforced Thermoplastics (SFT) pellet was used for injection moulding. E-glass fiber was used as reinforcement, and polyamide 66 (PA) and polypropylene containing modifying agent (MPP) were used as matrix resin respectively. In MPP, Polypropylene and maleic acid anhydride-modified polypropylene were mixed in the weight portion of 100:5. Injection moulded plate (2 mm in thickness, 96 mm in length and width) was prepared by a general-purpose injection molding machine. Table 1 shows injection moulding condition. Specimens used in tensile testing (Fig. 1) were obtained from injection moulded plate by water-jet machining. In this study, specimen name is described in the following order, L (LFT) or S (SFT) – Fiber name/matrix name.

Specimen	Control temperature °C	Mold temperature °C	Holding pressure MPa	Cooling time s
L-GFPA, S-GFPA	285	40	40	30
L-GFMPP, S-GFMPP	200	50	10	12

Table 1 Injection molded conditions of each specimen.

Fig. 1 Dimension of specimen used in static and impact tensile test.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Static and Impact Tensile Test

Static and impact tensile test were performed in order to evaluate the effect of the fiber length on impact tensile properties and strain rate dependency. Universal testing machine was used in static tensile test, and tension-type split Hopkinson pressure bar (Fig. 2 (a)) was used in impact tensile test. Specimens were fixed into the groove at the tip of input/output bar (Fig. 2 (b)).

3.2 Fiber length evaluation

Fiber length distribution was obtained as one of the internal structural evaluation of specimens. First, a test piece which was 11 mm length was cut out from the center of specimen. Matrix resin was

thermally decomposed in a muffle furnace on the condition of 500°C, 1h. After taking images of residual fibers by optical microscope, fiber length distribution was evaluated using image processing software.

Fig. 2 Tension type Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar used in this study.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Static Tensile Test

Fig. 3 shows stress strain curves of specimens in static tensile test. Comparing LFT specimens and SFT specimens, LFT specimens exhibit higher strength regardless of the type of matrix resin. This result is consistent with previous studies^[2].

Fig. 3 Stress strain curves of LFT and SFT specimens.

Fig. 4 shows fiber length distribution of L-GFPA and S-GFPA before static tensile test, and table 2 shows average fiber length of each specimen. In discontinuous fiber reinforced composite, sufficient reinforcing effect is obtained by fibers longer than critical fiber length. The critical fiber length of glass fiber in PA matrix is said to be about 300 μm. In this study, 87.6 % in L-GFPA and 69.8 % in S-GFPA of glass fibers have length greater than the critical fiber length. Furthermore, as the average fiber length of L-GFPA is as large as that of S-GFPA, it can be seen that fibers sufficiently longer than critical fiber length present in L-GFPA compared with S-GFPA. Consequently, characteristic of glass fiber is more utilized in L-GFPA, it shows higher strength than S-GFPA. In the case of GFMP, P,

residual fiber length of L-GFMPP after injection molding is longer than S-GFMPP, L-GFMPP shows higher strength than SFT specimen for the same reason of GFPA. However, the critical fiber length of glass fiber in MPP matrix is said to be about 1 mm, and strength improvement of GFMP by using LFT became smaller than GFPA.

Fig. 4 Fiber length distributions of L-GFPA and S-GFPA.

	L-GFPA	S-GFPA	L-GFMPP	S-GFMPP
Average residual fiber length μm	908	409	1055	493
Average fiber length after tensile test μm	722	374	990	458

Table 2 Comparisons of average fiber length in each specimen before and after static tensile test.

4.2 Impact Tensile Test

Fig. 5 shows the relationships between strength and strain rate. Comparing tensile strength at same strain rate, LFT shows higher strength than SFT same as the result of static tensile test. Tensile strength of all specimens was improved with increasing of strain rate. On the other hand, increment of strength, which is a representation of strain rate dependency, indicates different tendencies according to specimens. L-GFPA indicates strong strain rate dependency of strength compared with S-GFPA and its strength is significantly improved. As a result, strength difference between L-GFPA and S-GFPA is increased from 25.8 MPa (static) to 71.8 MPa (at strain rate of 100 s^{-1}). Therefore, the utility of LFT is revealed to be more remarkably exhibited under impact loading condition. In the case of GFMP, the difference of strain rate dependency between LFT and SFT specimen wasn't confirmed. The reason why effectiveness of LFT on impact properties is different according to the type of resin matrix is considered to be due to the difference of critical fiber length. In previous studies, it was revealed that glass fiber has strong strain rate dependency of tensile strength^[1]. Assuming the strain rate dependency of fiber/matrix interfacial strength is small, the critical fiber length becomes longer under impact loading than static loading. Therefore, much longer residual fibers are required in order to take advantage of high impact strength of glass fiber. As the average fiber length of L-GFPA is sufficiently long, high impact strength of glass fiber is exhibited. In the case of L-GFMPP, the ratio of residual fibers sufficiently longer than critical fiber length becomes smaller under impact loading, so LFT is less effective on improvement of impact properties.

Fig. 5 Strain rate dependency of tensile strength of LFT and SFT.

5 IMPACT STRENGTH PREDICTION

In discontinuous fiber reinforced composites, loading is transmitted to the individual fibers through shearing force of matrix resin. Actual injection molded composites have various micro structure such as fiber orientation and fiber length, so strength prediction model considering them have been proposed^[5, 6]. However, these are static strength prediction model, and applicability to impact loading condition isn't discussed. Under impact loading condition, strain rate dependencies of constituent material affect impact strength of injection molded composite. It is revealed that impact strength of reinforcement fiber particularly has a strong effect on impact mechanical properties of LFT. In this section, we extend the static strength prediction model for short-fiber reinforced composite, and we predict impact strength of LFT specimen.

Kelly and Tyson constructed a static strength prediction model of unidirectional short fiber reinforced composite by elastic – plastic analysis about single discontinuous fiber surrounded by matrix resin^[5]. As actual injection molded composites have fiber orientation distribution, Hukuda et al. extended the Kelly – Tyson model and proposed following equation^[6].

$$\sigma_c = \eta_0 \left\{ \sum_{l_i < l_c} \left(\frac{\sigma_f V_i l_i}{2l_c} \right) + \sum_{l_j > l_c} \left[\sigma_f V_j \left(1 - \frac{l_c}{2l_j} \right) \right] \right\} + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (1)$$

Here, η_0 is fiber orientation coefficient, σ_f is fiber strength, l_c is critical fiber length, l_i and l_j is the fiber length shorter and longer than l_c . V_i and V_j is fiber volume fraction, σ_m is yielding stress of matrix resin.

Fig. 6 Tensile strength of E-glass fiber and PA at various strain rates.

In this study, impact strength of L-GFPA and S-GFPA is estimated based on equation (1) considering strain rate dependencies of constituent materials. It was revealed that glass fiber has strong strain rate dependency of tensile strength^[1]. Matrix resin also has strain rate dependency of tensile strength. Fig. 6 shows strain rate dependencies of tensile strength in E-glass and PA. From Fig. 6, strength of constituent materials can be expressed by the following equations as a function of strain rate. The critical fiber length is calculated by equation (4), and changes with increasing of glass fiber strength.

$$\sigma_f = 0.0742\ln(\dot{\epsilon}) + 1.7595 \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_m = 0.1342\dot{\epsilon} + 79.234 \quad (3)$$

$$l_c = \frac{\sigma_f d}{2\tau} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 7 shows the result of impact strength prediction of L-GFPA and S-GFPA using equation (1-4).

Fig. 7 Comparisons of experimental and calculated impact strength of L-GFPA and S-GFPA.

From Fig. 7, predicted strength of L-GFPA and S-GFPA is almost consistent with the experimental value, and the static strength prediction model of injection moulded composite can be extended to under impact loading considering strain rate dependencies of constituent materials. Tensile strength of L-GFPA is greatly improved in the range from static to strain rate of 100 s⁻¹. After that, strength of L-GFPA is moderately increased. This tendency is similar to that of E-glass fiber shown in Fig. 6 (a), and improvement of L-GFPA strength is reveal to be due to the strain rate dependency of E-glass fiber. On the other hand, S-GFPA shows slight increasing of strength at any strain rate. It means that impact strength of E-glass fiber isn't sufficiently exhibited in the case of SFT.

The strength of L-CFPA whose fiber volume fraction is same with L-GFPA is also shown in Fig. 7. Here, we assume that strength of L-CFPA doesn't change because strain rate dependency of carbon fiber strength is known to be small. L-GFPA shows almost same level of strength with L-CFPA at strain rate of 150 s⁻¹. Since the load is applied at strain rate of over a few hundred s⁻¹ in automotive member, L-CFPA can be replaced with L-GFPA. It contributes to not only improvement of impact resistance but also cost reduction which is one of the challenges in the application of FRP.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the influence of residual fiber length on impact properties of injection moulded glass fiber reinforced composite was investigated. Impact tensile test using Long Fiber reinforced Thermoplastics (LFT) was conducted, and following conclusions were obtained.

(1) LFT showed higher strength than Song Fiber reinforced Thermoplastics (SFT) at any strain rate due to the fibers whose length is larger than the critical fiber length.

(2) LFT indicates strong strain rate dependency of strength compared with SFT and its strength is significantly improved. The utility of LFT is revealed to be more remarkably exhibited under impact loading condition.

(3) The static strength prediction model of injection moulded composite can be extended to under impact loading considering strain rate dependencies of constituent materials. Improvement of L-GFPA strength is revealed to be due to the strain rate dependency of E-glass fiber.

(4) L-GFPA shows almost same level of impact strength with L-CFPA, and the possibility that L-CFPA can be replaced with L-GFPA was revealed.

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